

Title: Deformation twinning as a displacive transformation: computational aspects of the phase-field model coupled with crystal plasticity

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Description: The dataset associated with this publication contains the finite-element codes and the simulation results related to the phase-field and crystal plasticity (coupled) modeling of the twin evolution and its interaction with plastic slip in a magnesium 4-grain unit cell.

Methodology: The finite-element codes were developed by using the AceGen system and the simulations are performed in AceFEM, both add-on packages of Mathematica. The postprocessing of the results has been done in the open-source platform Paraview.

File Formats: Finite-element codes are in .c format. The results are in two formats, the plot data in .csv format and the visualization data are in .vtk format.

Size: 50 GB

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Access Instructions: The full dataset is available upon request. Contact Mohsen Rezaee Hajidehi (mrezaee@ippt.pan.pl).

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